

TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS OF LEARNERS WITH LEARNING DISABILITIES IN MASARA CHILD FIND POLICY: A PHENOMENOLOGY

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Teachers' Perceptions of Learners with Learning Disabilities in Masara Child Find Policy: A Phenomenology

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Abstract

Inclusive education presented significant challenges globally, particularly for educators who navigated resource constraints and societal barriers. Despite initiatives like the Masara Child Find Policy in the Philippines, understanding teachers' perspectives on learners with disabilities remained underexplored, especially in Masara, Davao de Oro. This qualitative study employed in-depth interviews with five teachers actively involved in identifying and supporting students with disabilities at Masara Integrated School. Thematic analysis was used to identify patterns and themes within the data, guided by the phenomenological approach. Findings revealed teachers' perspectives on inclusive education, highlighting challenges in implementing the Masara Child Find Policy and supporting learners with disabilities. Teachers employed various strategies to identify and support students, yet faced obstacles such as limited resources and training. Despite challenges, teachers recognized the benefits of inclusive education for all learners. The study enhanced understanding of inclusive education within the Masara context, providing insights into teachers' perceptions and experiences. Recommendations included enhancing teacher training, resource allocation, and collaboration between stakeholders to promote effective implementation of inclusive education policies. These findings contributed to informed decision-making and policy formulation aimed at improving the educational experience of learners with disabilities in Masara and similar contexts.

Keywords: *special education, masara child find policy, phenomenological study*

Introduction

Inclusive education poses significant challenges for educators globally. Teachers often encounter obstacles rooted in a lack of confidence and resources essential for effectively supporting these learners (Longley & Craigo, 2021). Empirical evidence highlights similar challenges across countries such as Pakistan, Cambodia, and Vietnam, where cultural, societal, and resource-related barriers impede inclusive education efforts (Kamran et al., 2023; Rose et al., 2023; Phong, 2023).

In the Philippines, learners with disabilities face substantial hurdles due to inadequate resources and facilities, including specialized educational materials and trained personnel (Traya & Lopez, 2023). Despite implementing initiatives like the Masara Child Find Policy in Davao de Oro, understanding teachers' perceptions of learners with learning disabilities remains insufficiently explored. While recognizing the importance of inclusive education, there remains a gap in understanding the specific needs and challenges faced by learners with disabilities in Masara. Teachers desire to support these learners effectively but often feel unequipped due to limited training and resources.

Moreover, the literature underscores teachers' various challenges in implementing inclusive education policies and interventions. Early identification of learning disabilities is crucial for developing appropriate educational programs and interventions (Zain, 2020). Learners with learning disabilities often struggle with attention, hyperactivity, and motor coordination, impeding their learning progress (Ali et al., 2019; McLaren et al., 2022). Personalized approaches are essential to address individual needs effectively (Schalock et al., 2021), yet learners with disabilities may require additional support to navigate online spaces safely and effectively (Chiner et al., 2021). Challenges exist concerning teacher training, role clarity, and collaboration between special education and general education teachers (Billingsley et al., 2020; Molnar, 2019). Despite their pivotal role in developing interventions and implementing Individualized Education Programs (IEPs), special education teachers often face autonomy and training challenges (Auxier & Anderson, 2020; Lockwood, 2021; Lawrence, 2021).

Given these challenges and the urgent need to address them, this study aims to explore teachers' perspectives, beliefs, and challenges regarding inclusive education for learners with learning disabilities within the context of the Masara Child Find Policy in Masara, Davao de Oro, Philippines. While prior research has examined attitudes toward inclusive education, there is a lack of comprehensive exploration into educators' perceptions in Masara. This study seeks to enhance understanding of inclusive education and inform policy and practice in Masara and beyond by uncovering these perspectives.

This research study sought to discover the beliefs and perspectives of teachers at Masara Integrated School in Davao de Oro Division regarding students with learning disabilities within the Masara Child Find Policy framework. The research aimed to answer critical questions such as how teachers perceived students with learning disabilities, what actions or approaches they found compelling in fostering a positive learning environment, and how these factors impacted their professional satisfaction and well-being. Additionally, the study aimed to identify potential challenges or areas for improvement in supporting students with learning disabilities. By gaining insights into teachers' perceptions and experiences, the study aimed to inform strategies for enhancing the identification, support, and overall educational experience of learners with learning disabilities, ultimately improving the quality of education for teachers and learners in Masara Integrated School.

The primary objective of this research study was to delve into the lived experiences of teachers in implementing the Masara Child Find Policy. It aimed to achieve this through three specific objectives. Firstly, it sought to gain insight into teachers' perspectives regarding the inclusion of mainstream-tagged learners in inclusive education, alongside learners with learning disabilities, within the framework of the Masara Child Find Policy. Secondly, the study aimed to identify the strategies employed by teachers to effectively implement this policy. Finally, it aimed to determine teachers' insights and reflections on their experiences in implementing the Masara Child Find Policy. Through these objectives, the research aimed to contribute to a deeper understanding of the challenges and successes encountered by teachers in the implementation of this policy framework.

This study is mainly anchored on the social constructivism theory of Vygotsky (1978), who suggests that individuals construct their understanding of the world through interactions with others and their environment. In the context of this study, social constructivism suggests that teachers' views are shaped by their interactions with students, colleagues, parents, and the educational system's policies and practices.

Moreover, this study is seen through Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory (1977), which explains that individuals are influenced by multiple interconnected systems within their environment, ranging from the immediate microsystem to the broader macrosystem. In the context of teachers' perceptions of learners with learning disabilities in Masara, Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory provides valuable insights into the influence of shaping teachers' perspectives and experiences.

Furthermore, this study is also viewed from the Self-Efficacy Theory by Bandura (1977). The theory explains that an individual's belief in their capabilities to perform tasks and achieve goals plays a crucial role in determining their behavior, motivation, and level of success. In this study, the Self-Efficacy Theory suggests that teachers' beliefs in their abilities to support and educate learners with disabilities are crucial in influencing their perceptions and actions regarding the Masara Child Find Policy and its implementation.

Methodology

Research Design

The research design employed a qualitative approach, focusing on understanding teachers' lived experiences and perceptions in identifying learners with disabilities at Masara Integrated School. Qualitative research, as advocated by Creswell (2013), emphasized exploring complex phenomena in natural settings to gain insights into individuals' perspectives and behaviors. Through qualitative inquiry, the study sought to uncover underlying meanings and patterns inherent in the participants' narratives, providing valuable insights into implementing the Masara Child Find Policy.

Respondents

The research respondents for this study comprised five teachers from Masara Integrated School, chosen based on their active involvement in the initial process of identifying students with disabilities. These teachers played a pivotal role in observing, assessing, and referring students to the multidisciplinary team for further evaluation and support. Purposive sampling ensured that the selected participants possessed the expertise and experience relevant to the research topic, ensuring that their insights and perspectives were comprehensive and pertinent to the study's objectives.

One limitation of the study was the small sample size, as only five teachers from a single school, Masara Integrated School, participated. This limited sample may have constrained the generalizability of the findings to a broader population of educators. Furthermore, the study's exclusive focus on a specific geographical location may have hindered the transferability of the results to other educational contexts. Therefore, while the insights gained from this research provided valuable understanding within the context of Masara Integrated School, caution should have been exercised when applying these findings to different settings or populations.

Moreover, participants in the study were informed of their right to withdraw at any stage without facing any negative consequences. Clear withdrawal criteria were communicated during the informed consent process, ensuring that participants fully understood their rights and the procedure for withdrawing from the study. This transparent communication empowered participants to make informed decisions about their continued participation, contributing to the ethical conduct of the research.

Subsequently, the research took place at Masara Integrated School, examining how the Masara Child Find Policy was implemented within this educational environment. By focusing on a specific locale, the study aimed to provide in-depth insights into the practical application and challenges associated with the policy within a real-world context. This localized approach thoroughly explored the dynamics and intricacies of supporting learners with disabilities at Masara Integrated School, enhancing the study's relevance and applicability to similar educational settings.

Instruments

In addition to interview guides, various tools such as audio recording devices were utilized to capture interview sessions accurately. Furthermore, informed consent forms were employed to ensure that participants understood the study's purpose, procedures, and rights, while data storage facilities were utilized to store collected data securely, maintaining confidentiality and safeguarding participant information. These materials and instruments were essential to the research process, facilitating the systematic collection and protection

of data throughout the study duration. This description aligned with the recommendations of Patton (2015), who emphasized the importance of employing appropriate tools and procedures to ensure the integrity and reliability of qualitative research endeavors.

Procedure

After participant selection, data collection commenced through in-depth interviews with the selected teachers. These interviews were audio-recorded to capture participants' responses and insights accurately. Subsequently, the recorded interviews were transcribed verbatim to prepare the data for analysis. Thematic analysis was employed to identify patterns and themes within the data, with findings interpreted to derive meaningful insights and conclusions guided by the phenomenological approach suggested by Wertz (2023). Throughout these stages, meticulous procedures were followed to maintain consistency and rigor, ensuring the validity and reliability of the study findings.

Ethical Considerations

The study prioritized ethical considerations by adhering to established principles outlined in Belmont's Report and the Data Privacy Act. This approach also aligned with the ethical guidelines outlined by Parveen and Showkat (2017) and Resnik (2020). In this study, participants were provided with comprehensive information about the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits, and they were required to provide informed consent before participation. Measures were implemented to ensure confidentiality and data security, with all collected data stored securely and accessible only to authorized personnel. Respect for participants' autonomy was upheld by allowing them to withdraw from the study at any time without facing consequences. Additionally, the principle of beneficence guided the study's efforts to maximize benefits while minimizing risks to participants, ensuring that their welfare remained a priority. Furthermore, the principle of justice was upheld by ensuring fair treatment and equitable distribution of benefits and risks among participants. Overall, the study upheld ethical standards to protect participants' rights and promote the integrity of the research process.

Results and Discussion

Teacher's Perception on Including Mainstream-Tagged Learners within the Masara Child Find Policy Framework

Research Objective 1 as presented in Figure 1 was able to generate 3 main themes: Promote Equity and Access to Education, Navigate Challenges in Inclusive Education, and Support Inclusive Education through Policy Implementation, with 9 subthemes: Implementing Inclusive Policies and Practices, Ensuring Equal Opportunities for Learning, Utilizing Data-Driven Approaches for Monitoring Progress, Managing Classroom Interaction, Engaging with Parents, Supporting Students with Diverse Needs, Advocating for Inclusive Policies, Highlighting the Benefits of Inclusive Education, and Ensuring Equal Opportunities.

Promote Equity and Access to Education

Inclusive education is at the heart of promoting worldwide equity and access to education. By removing barriers and addressing disabilities, teachers can fully participate and thrive in the learning process. Participant 1 shared,

"In my classroom settings, learners with disabilities are treated equally with other learners." (P1, IDI 1)

"All learners, including those with disabilities, are treated equally, with tailored activities to match their capabilities." (P1, IDI 1)

Participant 2 agreed on the above ideas by ensuring a sense of belonging inside the classroom; she shared;

"Ensure a sense of belonging, create an open and psychologically safe environment, promote active listening, encourage participation, and maintain student motivation." (P2, IDI 2)

"First, ensure students feel they belong, then create an open, welcoming, and psychologically safe environment." (P2, IDI 2)

Implementing Inclusive Policies and Practices

Inclusive policies and practices in educational settings are essential for ensuring equitable opportunities for all learners, regardless of their backgrounds or abilities. Participant 2 shared,

"Ensure belongingness, a welcoming environment, and psychological safety. Promote active listening, encourage participation, and maintain student motivation." (P2, IDI 2)

"Prioritize belongingness, create a welcoming environment, ensure psychological safety, promote active listening, encourage participation, and maintain student motivation." (P2, IDI 2)

Participant 4 also shared her own experience on how she ensures students feel valued inside the classroom,

"I ensure all students are respected and given equal learning opportunities, employing differentiated instruction to accommodate diverse learning styles and needs." (P4, IDI 4)

"I ensure respect and equal learning opportunities for all students, employing differentiated instruction to cater to individual needs"

based on learning styles and development." (P4, IDI 4)

Participant 5 also makes sure students feel a sense of belongingness inside her classroom; she shared,

"In my classroom, I provide students with the sense of belongingness. Next, offer a welcoming environment. Lastly, diversify learning materials and develop rapport with each student." (P5, IDI 5)

"I foster belongingness, create a welcoming environment, diversify learning materials, and build rapport with each student." (P5, IDI 5)

Ensuring Equal Opportunities for Learning

Ensuring equal opportunities for learning is fundamental to creating an inclusive educational environment where every student has the chance to thrive regardless of their background, abilities, or circumstances. Participant 2 shared,

"Inclusive Education is when a school educates all children regardless of background or attainment level and educational needs." (P2, IDI 2)

"Inclusive education means educating all children regardless of background or needs, ensuring those with additional needs are included in mainstream classrooms." (P2, IDI 2)

Participant 5 also agreed by sharing,

"It means that all children have equal learning opportunities to learn and acquire skills without discrimination." (P5, IDI 5)

"It means all children have equal learning opportunities, free from discrimination." (P5, IDI 5)

Utilizing Data-Driven Approaches for Monitoring Progress

Utilizing data-driven approaches for monitoring progress in education involves gathering and analyzing relevant data to assess student performance, identify areas for improvement, and make informed decisions to enhance teaching and learning outcomes. Participant 1 understands the role of Masara Child Find Policy, she shared,

"Amhh, the Masara Child Find Policy was implemented because of the DepEd vision to provide an inclusive education for all learners, regardless of their background." (P1, IDI 1)

"The Masara Child Find Policy ensures inclusive education for all learners, aligned with DepEd's vision." (P1, IDI 1)

Participantn 3 supported this idea, she said,

"Our school, Masara Integrated School, implements the Child Find Policy, where learners with special education needs are allowed to thrive and become better." (P3, IDI 3)

"Masara Integrated School implements the Child Find Policy, supporting learners with special needs to thrive." (P3, IDI 3)

Furthermore, Participant 4 explains the importance of Masara Child Find Policy, she shared,

"My understanding about the Masara Child Find Policy is that it ensures that learners with disabilities are identified. And, making sure that they are tagged in the Learner Information System or LIS based on their learning needs." (P4, IDI 4):

"The Masara Child Find Policy ensures the identification and inclusion of learners with disabilities, documented in the Learner Information System." (P4, IDI 4).

This theme is supported by the idea of Hamenoo and Dayan (2021) which explains that inclusive education aims to eliminate barriers to inclusion by incorporating all learners, irrespective of their disabilities, into mainstream educational settings. This idea is supported by the Social Model of Disability proposed by Oliver (1990) who suggests that disability is not inherent within individuals but rather arises from the interaction between individuals and their environment.

Navigate Challenges in Inclusive Education

Inclusive education has many challenges that must be navigated to ensure the successful inclusion of all learners. Effectively navigating these challenges requires a comprehensive understanding of inclusive principles and the implementation of tailored strategies to support the diverse needs of all students.

Participant 1 shared how she manages classroom interaction to address these challenges in inclusive education;

"Learners within mainstream-tagged together with learners who have learning disabilities have separate learning activities that are suited to their needs " (P1, IDI 1)

"Mainstream and learners with disabilities have separate tailored activities, fostering inclusion." (P1, IDI 1)

In addition, Participant 3 experienced frustration in preparing learning activities for learners, she shared,

"Giisa ra nko ang activities para dili hago then same lang akong pag treat pud sa ilaha pud sa katong naay mga disabilities." (P3, IDI 3)

"Including mainstream and learners with disabilities in my classroom requires creating separate activities, but I integrate them equally." (P3, IDI 3)

Moreover, Participant 4 encountered challenges as she prepared her learning activities for learners with disabilities, she shared,

"As what I said, sa akong experience, challenge gyud kaau kay mag spend kag more time then dapat naa kay taas nga pasensya para mahimo nimo gihapon sa ilaha ang katong activities nga gibuhat nimo." (P4, IDI 4)

"It's challenging because I have to provide separate activities and spend extra time, requiring patience to ensure all students can complete the tasks." (P4, IDI 4)

Managing Classroom Interaction

Managing classroom interaction is crucial for creating an environment where all students can actively participate and engage in learning. Effective classroom interaction strategies enable teachers to facilitate discussions and contribute to a dynamic and inclusive learning atmosphere. Participant 1 has her own learning activities that are suited for her learners needs, she explain,

"Learners within mainstream-tagged together with learners who have learning disabilities have separate learning activities." (P1, IDI 1)

"Mainstream-tagged learners and those with learning disabilities have tailored activities, promoting inclusivity." (P1, IDI 1)

Furthermore, Participant 3 also supported the idea by sharing,

"Giisa ra nko kay sa activities, ang, ang, activities para dili hago then same lang akong pag treat pud sa ilaha pud sa katong naay mga disabilities." (P3, IDI 3)

"Including mainstream-tagged and learners with disabilities in one class is challenging to create separate activities, but I integrate them together with equal treatment." (P3, IDI 3)

Consequently, Participant 5 encounter behavioral problems of learners with disabilities, she shared,

"The challenges that I had encountered in my classroom ma'am are behavioral issues of the students, approaches and methods to be used in teaching, and also the expectation of the parents ma'am." (P5, IDI 5)

"I face challenges with student behavior, teaching methods, and parental expectations, especially as I'm not a SPED teacher." (P5, IDI 5)

Engaging with Parents

Engaging with parents is crucial for fostering a supportive and collaborative educational environment that promotes student success. By establishing strong partnerships between educators and parents, schools can effectively communicate and work together to address the diverse needs of students. Participant 4 explain the importance of parents acceptance of the learners condition, she shared,

"I guess one of the major challenged that I encounter is on the acceptance of parents regarding the learning status of their child because sometimes there are parents who are in denial regarding the learning need, or ahmm, status of their children (P4, IDI 4)

"A major challenge is parental acceptance of their child's learning needs; some are in denial, making communication difficult." (P4, IDI 4)

However, Participant 5 felt pressured on parents expectation, she explained,

"The challenges that I had encountered in my classroom ma'am are behavioral issues of the students, approaches and methods to be used in teaching, and also the expectation of the parents ma'am." (P5, IDI 5)

"Challenges include student behavior, teaching methods, and parental expectations." (P5, IDI 5)

Supporting Students with Diverse Needs

Supporting students with diverse needs is a fundamental aspect of creating an inclusive educational environment where every learner can thrive. This entails implementing tailored strategies, accommodations, and resources to address individual learning styles, abilities, and challenges. Participant 1 explain the importance of separate learning activities for learners, she shared,

"Learners within mainstream-tagged together with learners who have learning disabilities have separate learning activities that are suited to their needs. This also allowed learners with disabilities to feel included within the classroom setting." (P1, IDI 1)

"Mainstream-tagged learners and those with disabilities have separate tailored activities, fostering inclusivity." (P1, IDI 1)

In addition, Participant 2 also shared the importance of cooperative learning

"For me, a great way to implement inclusive Education in the classroom is to present task and activities in a way that encourages cooperative learning. By learning in groups, students are all given the opportunity to participate." (P2, IDI 2)

"Encouraging cooperative learning fosters inclusive education by providing all students with opportunities to participate." (P2, IDI 2)

Participant 2 also agreed by saying,

"The challenges that I had encountered in my classroom ma'am are behavioral issues of the students, approaches and methods to be used in teaching, and also the expectation of the parents ma'am (P5, IDI 5)

"Challenges include student behavioral issues, teaching approaches, and parental expectations, especially challenging without specialized training." (P5, IDI 5)

The second theme is supported by the study of Chadwick (2022), who found that individuals with intellectual disabilities know online risks and can largely navigate them effectively. A supporting theory for this idea can be found in Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). According to Vygotsky, the ZPD refers to the difference between what a learner can do without assistance and what they can achieve with guidance and support from a more knowledgeable other, such as a teacher or peer (Vygotsky, 1978).

Support Inclusive Education through Policy Implementation

This serves as a critical framework for fostering equitable learning environments where all students, regardless of ability, have access to quality education. Participant 1 supported the inclusive education policy, she shared,

"Our school ofcourse support the implementation of inclusive Education since we do not exclude those learners with disabilities." (P1, IDI 1)

"Our school supports inclusive education by not excluding learners with disabilities." (P1, IDI 1)

Participant 3 also supported this idea, she shared,

"Ahh, we support Masara Child Find Policies since hindi naman namin sila.. ahh, but we support the Masara Find Policy." (P3, IDI 3)

"We support the Masara Child Find Policies, even though we do not directly include learners with special needs or disabilities." (P3, IDI 3)

Moreover, Participant 5 ensures that Masara Find Policy allows learner to have an equal opportunity to learn, she shared,

"The benefits of Masara Child Find Policy to the learners is that those who are tagged lerners were given an equal opportunity to learn." (P5, IDI 5)

"The Masara Child Find Policy ensures equal learning opportunities for tagged learners." (P5, IDI 5)

Advocating for Inclusive Policies

Advocating for inclusive policies is essential for fostering a learning environment that celebrates diversity and ensures equitable access to education for all individuals. This proactive stance promotes a culture of acceptance, respect, and support within educational institutions. Participant 1 shared,

"Our school ofcourse support the implementation of inclusive Education since we do not exclude those learners with disabilities." (P1, IDI 1)

"Our school supports inclusive education by not excluding learners with disabilities." (P1, IDI 1)

In addition, Participant 2 also agreed,

"Yes, the Masara Child Find Policy supports the implementation of inclusive Education because it helps learners with disabilities be given an opportunity to become better and included." (P2, IDI 2)

"The Masara Child Find Policy supports inclusive education by providing opportunities for learners with disabilities to improve and be included." (P2, IDI 2)

In the same vein, participant 4 added,

"I would say that the Masara Child Find Policy supports the implementation of the inclusive Education since it ensures that learners with disabilities are identified, located, and tag in the LIS or Learners Information System. (P4, IDI 4)

"The Masara Child Find Policy supports inclusive education by identifying and supporting learners with disabilities, raising awareness, and ensuring no learner is left behind." (P4, IDI 4)

Highlighting the Benefits of Inclusive Education

Highlighting the benefits of inclusive education is essential for advocating its implementation and fostering understanding of its positive impact. Inclusive education not only promotes academic achievement but also enhances social skills, reduces stigma, and fosters a sense of belonging among all learners. Participant 2 shared,

"For instance teaching students with special needs in inclusive education can lead to, first is the greater gains in academic literacy, math, and social studies, better communication and social skills, fewer absences, less disruptive behavior and more motivation to work and to learn." (P2, IDI 2)

"Inclusive education for students with special needs can lead to academic, social, and behavioral improvements." (P2, IDI 2)

In addition, participant 3 agreed,

"The benefits of inclusive education for mainstream tagged learners is dili sila maulahi, ma feel gihapon na pareha lang sila tanan." (P3, IDI 3)

"Inclusive education ensures mainstream learners don't feel left out, fostering a sense of equality." (P3, IDI 3)

Participant 4 also shared,

"Inclusive education offers equal opportunities and accommodations for all learners, recognizing their uniqueness and providing additional funds for assistive materials through Department of Education programs." (P4, IDI 4)

"Inclusive education provides equal opportunities and accommodations for all learners, embracing their uniqueness and providing additional resources through programs like the Department of Education's assistance fund." (P4, IDI 4)

Ensuring Equal Opportunities

Ensuring equal opportunities is essential in creating an educational environment where every individual has the chance to thrive and succeed. By prioritizing fairness and equity, educational institutions can mitigate disparities and provide all learners with the resources and support they need to reach their full potential. Participant 1 shared,

"Our school ofcourse support the implementation of inclusive Education since we do not exclude those learners with disabilities." (P1, IDI 1)

"Our school supports inclusive education by not excluding learners with disabilities." (P1, IDI 1)

Moreover, participant 3 also supported the idea,

"Ahh, we support Masara Child Find Policies since hindi naman namin sila.. ahhh... ini include sa akoo, sa akin, hindi ko naman sila ini include na meron silang special needs or may disabilities, but we support the Masara Find Policy." (P3, IDI3)

"We support the Masara Child Find Policies because even though we don't directly include them with special needs or disabilities, we endorse the policy." (P3, IDI3)

Participant 5 also shared,

"The benefits of Masara Child Find Policy to the learners is that those who are tagged lerners were given an equal opportunity to learn." (P5, IDI 5)

"The Masara Child Find Policy ensures equal learning opportunities for tagged learners." (P5, IDI 5)

Theme 3 is supported by the findings of Paloniemi et al. (2021), who found that in Finland, the National Core Curriculum mandates that responsibilities related to developing new pedagogical documents should be clearly defined in the local curricula of municipalities and schools. This finding is supported by Decentralization Theory of Oates (1972) which advocates for the devolution of authority and resources to lower levels of the education system to promote effective governance, enhance local capacity-building, and facilitate tailored solutions to address specific educational challenges and priorities.

Teachers Strategies being Employed to Implement the Masara Child Find Policy Effectively

Research Objective 2, as presented in Figure 2, was able to generate 3 main themes: Identify Students that Required Additional Support, Implement Procedures Outlined in the Masara Child Find Policy, and Ensure Support for Learners with Learning Disabilities with 9 subthemes: Conducting Assessment and Observation, Involving Parents and Collaboration, Utilizing Standardized Tools and Previous Adviser Input, Following DepEd Guidelines, Utilizing Strategies for Effective Implementation, Promoting Collaborative Efforts, Supporting Individualized Needs, Enhancing Teacher Preparedness, and Facilitating Resource Allocation.

Identify Learners who Required Additional Support

To identify learners requiring additional support, a comprehensive approach involving observation, assessment, and consultation is crucial. Observation allows for the recognition of behavioral and academic patterns, while assessments provide concrete data on a student's strengths and needs. Participant 1 shared,

"To identify students who may require additional support, I conduct a one on one assessment to the learners." (P1, IDI 1)

"I conduct one-on-one assessments to identify students needing additional support." (P1, IDI 1)

Participant 3 also stipulated,

"First you have to conduct assessment, kay lisod pud kaayo na moderetso pud kag, kanang tudlo nga naa siya'y disabilities, so mag conduct muna ng assessment." (P3, IDI 3)

"First, conduct assessments to identify disabilities and support needs." (P3, IDI 3)

In addition, participant 5 explain,

"In my own opinion ma'am, these are the following steps in identifying students who may require support under the Masara Child Find Policy: First, the child is being evaluated, next is provide a range of learning materials. Next is focus on students attention." (P5, IDI 5)

"I believe the steps to identify students needing support under the Masara Child Find Policy include evaluation, providing learning materials, and focusing on attention." (P5, IDI 5)

Conducting Assessment and Observation

Conducting assessments and observations plays a crucial role in identifying students who may require additional support in their learning journey. By systematically evaluating students' abilities, educators can gain valuable insights to tailor interventions to meet diverse learning needs. Participant 1 shared

"To identify students who may require additional support, I conduct a one on one assessment to the learners." (P1, IDI 1)

"I conduct one-on-one assessments to identify students needing additional support." (P1, IDI 1)

In the same vein, participant 3 also added,

"First you have to conduct assessment, kay lisod pud kaayo na moderetso pud kag, kanang tudlo nga naa siya'y disabilities, so mag conduct muna ng assessment." (P3, IDI 3)

"First, conduct assessments to identify disabilities." (P3, IDI 3)

Participant 4 also shared,

"I don't have a specific step-by-step strategy, but I identify students needing support based on their performance in standardized tests like EGRA and Phil-Iri." (P4, IDI 4)

"I identify students needing support based on observations and performance assessments, including standardized tests and classroom behavior." (P4, IDI 4)

Involving Parents and Collaboration

Involving parents and fostering collaboration between educators and families is essential for creating a supportive and enriching educational environment. By working together, parents and teachers can better understand and address the needs of students, promote consistent learning experiences, and enhance overall academic and personal development. Participant 1 explain,

"Examples of providing collaboration is through attending Parents Teachers Conferences. (P1, IDI 1)."

"Collaboration examples include attending Parent-Teacher Conferences." (P1, IDI 1)

Participant 3 agreed by sharing,

"Ahh, through parent-teachers conference, dapat mayroong meeting sa teacher and the parent." (P3, IDI 3)"

"Through parent-teacher conferences, there should be a meeting between the teacher and parent to discuss the child's needs." (P3, IDI 3)

Participant 5 also added,

"For me the example of this collaborating with other stakeholders is through teacher and parents collaboration (P5, IDI 5)"

"Collaboration with other stakeholders, such as teacher and parent collaboration, is crucial because parents understand their child's needs best." (P5, IDI 5)

Utilizing Standardized Tools and Previous Adviser Input

Utilizing standardized tools and input from previous advisers are valuable methods in identifying students who may require additional support in their learning journey. These tools and insights offer educators essential data and perspectives to assess student performance, understand their needs, and tailor interventions effectively. Participant 1 shared,

"To identify students who may require additional support, I conduct a one on one assessment to the learners." (P1, IDI 1)

"I conduct one-on-one assessments to identify students needing additional support." (P1, IDI 1)

In the same vein, participant 4 also added,

"I don't have a specific step-by-step strategy for identifying students needing support, but it's based on observing their performance" (P4, IDI 4)

"I don't have a specific step-by-step strategy for identifying students needing support." (P4, IDI 4)

In addition, participant 5 also shared,

"In my own opinion ma'am, these are the following steps in identifying students who may require support under the Masara Child Find Policy by focusing on students attention." (P5, IDI 5)

"I believe the steps for identifying students needing support under the Masara Child Find Policy include evaluation, providing learning materials, and focusing on students' attention." (P5, IDI 5)

Theme 1 is supported by the findings outlined by Campado et al. (2023). Their study found that acquiring modern Assistive Technology, upskilling teachers, and establishing links with stakeholders mirroring participants' emphasis on observation, consultation, and collaboration. Moreover, Social Model of Disability provides a theoretical framework of this findings which highlights the role of societal attitudes, structures, and policies in shaping the experiences of individuals with disabilities (Oliver, 1996)

Implement Procedures Outlined in the Masara Child Find Policy

Implementing the procedures outlined in the Masara Child Find Policy involves systematic identification and support for learners needing assistance. This includes conducting thorough assessments, providing appropriate learning materials, and fostering parental involvement. Participant 1 shared,

"We can ensure this by following the guidelines provided by the DepEd about the Child Find Policy." (P1, IDI 1)

"Following DepEd guidelines on the Child Find Policy ensures this." (P1, IDI 1)

Participant 3, agreed by saying,

"Sinusunod namin yung mga guidelines na binibigay ng DepEd." (P3, IDI 3)

"We follow the guidelines provided by DepEd." (P3, IDI 3)

Participant 4 also shared,

"Ensuring students needing support are tagged in LIS and maintaining proper communication with parents regarding support strategies and employing appropriate methods to cater to identified student needs." (P4, IDI 4)

"Ensuring all students needing support are tagged in LIS and maintaining proper communication with parents regarding support strategies." (P4, IDI 4)

Following DepEd Guidelines

Following DepEd guidelines is essential for maintaining consistency, quality, and compliance within the educational system. These guidelines serve as a framework for educators and administrators to ensure that educational practices align with established standards and regulations set forth by the Department of Education. Participant 1 agreed,

"We can ensure this by following the guidelines provided by the DepEd about the Child Find Policy." (P1, IDI 1)

"Following DepEd guidelines on the Child Find Policy ensures compliance." (P1, IDI 1)

Moreover, participant 3 explained,

"Sinusunod namin yung mga guidelines na binibigay ng DepEd." (P3, IDI 3)

"We follow the guidelines provided by DepEd." (P3, IDI 3)

In the same vein, participant 4 also shared,

"There is no specific standardized tool that would identify students with learning needs, and as an adviser, it is more plausible for me like the use of observation inside my classroom because it could happened any time." (P4, IDI 4)

"As an adviser, I rely on observation in my classroom since there's no specific standardized tool for identifying students with learning needs." (P4, IDI 4)

Utilizing Strategies for Effective Implementation

Utilizing strategies for effective implementation is essential in ensuring the successful execution of educational policies and initiatives. By employing targeted approaches and methodologies, educators can overcome challenges, maximize resources, and optimize outcomes in various educational settings. Participant 2 shared,

"Make adjustment, you make ahh, modifications to your strategy that may increase the possibility of it and create a plan for how to implement these changes." P2, IDI 2)

"Adjust strategies to enhance effectiveness and achieve set goals, brainstorm potential modifications, and create an implementation plan for improvement." (P2, IDI 2)

In the same manner, participant 3 shared,

"Maibigay ko yung kailangan ng learners, mas maraming materials, mas effective yung pagtuturo." P3, IDI3)

"I provide what learners need, more materials make teaching more effective." (P3, IDI3)

Moreover, participant 5 added,

"By implementing these strategies, it help the teachers to be more effective to every student and to those learners with learning disabilities. Students with learning disabilities needs a SPED teacher." (P5, IDI 5)

"Implementing these strategies helps teachers be more effective for all students, including those with learning disabilities who may require a SPED teacher." (P5, IDI 5)

Promoting Collaborative Efforts

Promoting collaborative efforts in education is essential for creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment. By fostering partnerships among educators, parents, administrators, and community members, schools can effectively address diverse needs and ensure the success of all learners. Participant 2 shared,

"Okay, we need to create opportunities to listen to all our children, develop scaffolded approach to learning and provide support for them in all ways, can be benefit of all children in your class." (P2, IDI 2)

"We must listen to our students, adapt learning approaches, understand each child's needs, and provide comprehensive support for the benefit of all." (P2, IDI 2)

In the same vein, participant 4 shared,

"I mentioned three challenges in implementing the Masara Child Find Policy: parental acceptance, lack of expertise, and time constraints." (P4, IDI 4)

"I identified three challenges in implementing the Masara Child Find Policy: parental acceptance, lack of expertise, and time constraints. Schools should offer training and assign knowledgeable staff to support students effectively." (P4, IDI 4)

Participant 5 supported this idea, she shared

"Sama sa akong giingon ma'am na magconduct nlang og training para sa mga teacher para maka teach sa mga bata nga with learning disabilities." (P5, IDI 5)

"As I mentioned earlier, conducting training for teachers to teach students with learning disabilities would aid in implementing positive behavioral interventions and supporting these learners effectively." (P5, IDI 5)

Theme 2 of Objective Number 2 aligned with the findings of Molnar (2019), who explained that legal mandates regarding the Least Restrictive Environment (LRE) require special education teachers to collaborate closely with educators across various subject areas. Furthermore, this finding is supported by the Ecological Systems Theory of Bronfenbrenner (1989) which provides a theoretical foundation for understanding the collaboration between special education and general education teachers.

The theory underscores the importance of collaborative efforts to promote inclusive education practices and support the diverse needs of all students.

Ensure Support for Learners with Learning Disabilities

Supporting learners with learning disabilities is essential for fostering inclusive education environments. It involves providing tailored assistance and accommodations to ensure these students receive the necessary support to thrive academically and socially. Participant 4 shared,

To address these, the school or DepEd should organize seminars and programs to equip teachers with necessary knowledge, strategies, and methods, or designate a specific teacher with expertise to focus on and support these students. (P4, IDI 4)

"To address challenges with the Masara Child Find Policy, such as parental acceptance, teacher knowledge, and time constraints, the school or DepEd should organize seminars to equip teachers or designate specialized support teachers." (P4, IDI 4)

Participant 5 added,

"Sama sa akong giingon ma'am na magconduct nlang og training para sa mga teacher para maka teach sa mga bata nga with learning disabilities and will help me in implementing positive behavioral intervention for learners with learning disabilities po." (P5, IDI 5)

"Similar to what I said earlier, conducting training for teachers to teach children with learning disabilities would help me implement positive behavioral interventions and support these learners." (P5, IDI 5)

In addition, participant 2 also shared,

"Okay, we need to create opportunities to listen to all our children, develop scaffolded approach to learning, be aware of the specific needs of every child in your class, provide support for them in all ways, can be benefit of all children in your class." (P2, IDI 2)

"We need to listen to all our children, develop a scaffolded approach to learning, be aware of each child's specific needs, and provide support in every way possible for the benefit of all children in the class." (P2, IDI 2)

Supporting Individualized Needs

Supporting individualized needs in education involves tailoring approaches to meet the unique requirements of each learner, ensuring inclusivity and personalized support for optimal academic and personal growth. Participant 1 shared,

"We can ensure this by following the guidelines provided by the DepEd about the Child Find Policy." (P1, IDI 1)

"We ensure this by adhering to DepEd's Child Find Policy guidelines." (P1, IDI 1)

Moreover, participant 2 shared her strategies in supporting learners with special needs. She said,

"Okay, we need to create opportunities to listen to all our children, develop scaffolded approach to support them in all ways, and can benefit them in our class." (P2, IDI 2)

"We must listen to all students, adopt a scaffolded approach to learning, understand each child's specific needs, and provide support, benefiting all students." (P2, IDI 2)

Also, participant 4 added,

"There is no specific standardized tool that would identify students with learning needs, and as an adviser, it is more plausible for me like the use of observation inside my classroom because it could happened any time." (P4, IDI 4)

"As an adviser, I rely on classroom observation since there's no specific standardized tool for identifying students' learning needs." (P4, IDI 4)

Enhancing Teacher Preparedness

Enhancing teacher preparedness is essential for ensuring effective education delivery and student support. It involves providing educators with the necessary knowledge, skills, and resources to address diverse learning needs, navigate challenges, and implement inclusive teaching practices. Participant 4 shared,

"To address these, DepEd should conduct seminars to equip teachers with necessary knowledge, or assign specific teachers trained to handle such students." (P4, IDI 4)

"To tackle these, DepEd should organize seminars to provide teachers with essential knowledge and assign trained teachers to support these students." (P4, IDI 4)

Participant 5 also shared,

"Sama sa akong giingon ma'am na magconduct nlang og training para sa mga teacher para maka teach sa mga bata nga with learning disabilities." (P5, IDI 5)

"As I mentioned earlier, conducting training for teachers to teach children with learning disabilities would help in implementing

positive behavioral intervention and supporting those learners." (P5, IDI 5)

In addition, participant 2 shared,

"Make adjustment to achieve your goals and consider brainstorming for potential adjustment to the policy that can help increase its effectiveness and create a plan to implement these changes." (P2, IDI 2).

"Adjust your strategy to increase its effectiveness, brainstorm potential modifications to the policy, and create a plan for implementing these changes." (P2, IDI 2)

Facilitating Resource Allocation

Facilitating resource allocation in educational settings involves the strategic distribution of resources such as funding, personnel, and materials to ensure optimal support for teaching and learning activities. Participant 1 shared,

"We can ensure this by following the guidelines provided by the DepEd about the Child Find Policy." (P1, IDI 1)

"Following DepEd guidelines on the Child Find Policy ensures this." (P1, IDI 1)

In the same vein, participant 3 added,

"Sinusunod namin yung mga guidelines na binibigay ng DepEd." (P3, IDI 3)

"We follow the guidelines provided by DepEd." (P3, IDI 3)

In addition, participant 5 explained,

"By implementing these strategies, it help the teachers to be more effective to every student and to those learners with learning disabilities. Students with learning disabilities needs a SPED teacher." (P5, IDI 5)

"Implementing these strategies helps teachers be more effective, especially for students with learning disabilities who may need a SPED teacher in a special school or classroom." (P5, IDI 5)

Theme 3 is supported by Perera et al. (2019), who explained that special education teachers are tasked with assessing students' progress toward individualized goals, managing paperwork to track these goals, making daily decisions with other educators, and communicating with families and other support providers. This finding is further supported by the Theory of Differentiated Instruction which emphasized the multifaceted nature of special education teaching roles and the importance of individualized, student-centered approaches to instruction and support (Tomlinson & Mctighe, 2006).

Teachers' insights in implementing the Masara Child Find Policy.

Research Objective 3, as presented in Figure 3, was able to generate 3 main themes: Perspective on the Implementation of the Masara Child Find Policy, Evaluate the Effectiveness of the Masara Child Find Policy, and Influence Approach to Implement and Adhere to the Masara Child Find Policy with 9 subthemes: Needing for Teacher Training and Support, Understanding the Significance of policy, Suggesting for Policy Enhancement, Addressing Challenges and Limitations in Effectiveness, Recognizing Initial Successes, Suggesting Improvements for Policy Enhancement, Recognizing Personal Limitations and Seeking Improvement, Emphasizing the Importance of Establishing Relationships, and Advocating for Comprehensive Approaches and Collaborative Efforts.

Perspective on the Implementation of the Masara Child Find Policy

Perspective on the implementation of the Masara Child Find Policy is crucial for enhancing educational support systems. By examining its effectiveness, stakeholders can identify areas for improvement and ensure equitable access to education for all learners. Participant 1 shared,

"Implementation of Child Find Policy in our school is somehow helpful to those tags learners, however, we teacher are not equipped to teach those learners." (P1, IDI 1)

"The Child Find Policy implementation in our school is helpful for tagged learners, but teachers lack the necessary training to teach them." (P1, IDI 1)

Participant 3 also shared,

"Child Find Policy in our school is good, but we need a teacher who are skilled to teach these learners. Maski isa lang na SPED teacher na ma provide nila." (P3, IDI3)

"The Child Find Policy is good in our school, but we need skilled teachers, even just one SPED teacher they can provide." (P3, IDI3)

In addition, participant 5 also said,

"My insight is that the Department of Education has issued this Child Find Policy to help those learners with learning disabilities in

continuing their education." (P5, IDI 5)

"My insight is that the Department of Education issued the Child Find Policy to support learners with disabilities in continuing their education." (P5, IDI 5)

Needing for Teacher Training and Support

In the realm of education, ensuring that teachers receive adequate training and support is paramount. Teachers play a pivotal role in shaping the learning experiences of students, and their level of preparation significantly impacts the quality of education delivered. Participant 1 shared,

"The teacher who will handle learners with disabilities should be given proper training." (P1, IDI 1)

"Special education teachers need proper training." (P1, IDI 1)

Moreover, participant 3 also shared,

"Kagaya ng sinabi ko kanina, ahh dapat magbigay yung DepEd ng SPED teachers." (P3, IDI 3)

"Like I said earlier, DepEd should provide SPED teachers." (P3, IDI 3)

In addition, participant 4 also suggested,

"I suggest that the Department of Education or higher authorities organize seminars and orientations on the Child Find Policy for teachers and advisers lacking special education background. This would help us handle, administer, identify, and employ appropriate strategies effectively." (P4, IDI 4)

"DEPED should hold seminars on the Child Find Policy for teachers without special education backgrounds to help them handle and identify strategies." (P4, IDI 4)

Understanding the Significance of policy

Understanding the significance of policy in education is crucial as it serves as the foundation for guiding decision-making, implementing strategies, and evaluating outcomes within educational systems. Participant 1 shared,

"Implementation of Child Find Policy in our school is somehow helpful to those tags learners, however, we teacher are not equipped to teach those learners." (P1, IDI 1)

"The Child Find Policy implementation in our school benefits tagged learners, but teachers lack the necessary training." (P1, IDI 1)

In the same vein, participant 3 also explained,

"Child Find Policy in our school is good, but we need a teacher who are skilled to teach these learners. Maski isa lang na SPED teacher na ma provide nila." (P3, IDI 3)

"The Child Find Policy in our school is good, but we need skilled teachers, even just one SPED teacher they can provide." (P3, IDI 3)

In addition, participant 5 shared,

"My insight is that the Department of Education has issued this Child Find Policy to help those learners with learning disabilities in continuing their education." (P5, IDI 5)

"I believe the Department of Education issued the Child Find Policy to support learners with learning disabilities in their education." (P5, IDI 5)

Suggesting for Policy Enhancement

Policy enhancement suggestions are crucial for refining existing frameworks, ensuring effectiveness, and addressing emerging needs. These recommendations often stem from insights gathered through practical experiences and observations, aiming to optimize policy outcomes and better serve stakeholders. Participant 3 shared,

"Child Find Policy in our school is good, but we need a teacher who are skilled to teach these learners. Maski isa lang na SPED teacher na ma provide nila." (P3, IDI 3).

"The Child Find Policy in our school is good, but we need at least one skilled SPED teacher to teach these learners." (P3, IDI 3)

Participant 4 also added,

"My suggestion is that the Department Education or the higher authorities should conduct a series of seminars, orientations regarding the Child Find Policy." (P4, IDI 4)

"I suggest the Department of Education should conduct seminars on the Child Find Policy for teachers and advisers without special

education backgrounds to better equip them in handling, identifying." (P4, IDI 4)

In addition, participant 5 suggested,

"My suggestion for the enhancement of Masara Child Find Policy will be ahh.. the students or those learners with learning disabilities must be assessed by the doctor so that they will be given a chance to check and assess their condition." (P5, IDI 5)

"I suggest enhancing the Masara Child Find Policy by having students with learning disabilities assessed by doctors to better understand their condition and enable them to showcase their skills in the classroom." (P5, IDI 5)

Theme 1 of objective number 3 emphasized the need to support learners with learning disabilities. These findings aligned with the idea of Salmerón et al. (2019), who discovered that individuals with intellectual disabilities require personalized support across various life domains. This finding is supported by the idea of Social Model of Disability Theory in which explains that educators, policymakers, and support professionals can work collaboratively to create inclusive environments and provide personalized support that enables learners with learning disabilities to fully participate in society while respecting their autonomy and promoting their well-being (Oliver, 1983).

Evaluate the Effectiveness of the Masara Child Find Policy

The effectiveness of the Masara Child Find Policy is pivotal in ensuring equitable access to education for all learners. By systematically identifying and tagging students with learning needs, the policy aims to provide tailored support and interventions. Participant 1 shared,

"In my observation, the effectiveness of the Masara Child Find Policy is not that effective." (P1, IDI 1)

"In my observation, the Masara Child Find Policy is not very effective." (P1, IDI 1)

Participant 4 added,

"I believe the initial phase of implementing the Masara Child Find Policy was effective, as it resulted in additional funds for purchasing learning materials for students with special needs." (P4, IDI 4)

"I find the initial phase of the Masara Child Find Policy effective, securing extra funds for special needs students' learning materials, despite our limited understanding of the policy." (P4, IDI 4)

Furthermore, participant 5 also said,

"I guess ma'am, it needs more improvement pa. Dapat pud ang teacher, pahibal on kung unsaon pag identify sa bata og unsay buhatan about ana, tapos ma'am, para sa akoo, maglisod gyud mi as a teacher kay dili man mi SPED teacher po." (P5, IDI 5)

"I think it needs further improvement. Teachers should be informed on how to identify and address the needs of students, but as for us, it's challenging because we're not SPED teachers." (P5, IDI 5)

Addressing Challenges and Limitations in Effectiveness

Addressing challenges and limitations in effectiveness is crucial for ensuring that educational policies and practices meet their intended goals. By identifying and overcoming obstacles, educators can optimize the implementation of strategies to better support student learning and success. Participant 1 shared,

"Ahh hindi siya masyadong effective kasi halimbawa para sa akin, kahit ano nlang ang maibigay ko para lang unsay ma fit sa iyahang needs, dili gyud siya effective kay dili man ko SPED teacher." (P1, IDI 3)

"It's not very effective because, for example, whatever I provide just to fit their needs, it's still not effective because I'm not a SPED teacher." (P1, IDI 3)

In addition, participant 4 supported,

"I could say that the first phase on the implementation of Masara Child Find Policy was effective, though we don't have that ample knowledge as to what specifically this policy all about." (P4, IDI 4)

"I think the initial phase of implementing the Masara Child Find Policy was effective. Although we lacked ample knowledge about the specifics of the policy, our efforts in tagging learners with learning gaps." (P4, IDI 4)

Participant 5 shared,

"I guess ma'am, it needs more improvement pa. Dapat pud ang teacher, pahibal on kung unsaon pag identify sa bata og unsay buhatan about ana, tapos ma'am, para sa akoo, maglisod gyud mi as a teacher kay dili man mi SPED teacher po." (P5, IDI 5)

"I think it still needs improvement. Teachers should be informed about how to identify and address the needs of these students. Personally, as a non-SPED teacher, it's challenging for us." (P5, IDI 5)

Recognizing Initial Successes

Recognizing initial successes in educational policies and practices is crucial for fostering continuous improvement and ensuring positive outcomes for students. By acknowledging achievements, educators can build momentum and motivation to further enhance teaching methods and support systems. Participant 1 shared,

"In my observation, the effectiveness of the Masara Child Find Policy is not that effective." (P1, IDI 1)

"In my observation, the effectiveness of the Masara Child Find Policy is limited." (P1, IDI 1)

Participant 4 further explained,

"I believe the initial phase of implementing the Masara Child Find Policy was effective, despite our limited understanding of its specifics. Tagging learners with learning gaps led to additional funds for purchasing materials for students with special needs." (P4, IDI 4)

"I believe the initial phase of implementing the Masara Child Find Policy was effective, resulting in additional funds for purchasing learning materials for students with special needs." (P4, IDI 4)

Similarly, participant 5 shared,

"I guess ma'am, it needs more improvement pa. Dapat pud ang teacher, pahibal on kung unsaon pag identify sa bata og unsay buhatan about ana, tapos ma'am, para sa akoo, maglisod gyud mi as a teacher kay dili man mi SPED teacher po." (P5, IDI 5)

"I think it still needs improvement. Teachers should be informed on how to identify and address the needs of these students, but for us teachers who are not SPED-trained, it's challenging." (P5, IDI 5)

Suggesting Improvements for Policy Enhancement

Addressing policy shortcomings often requires insightful recommendations for improvement, aimed at enhancing its effectiveness. Suggestions for policy enhancement play a crucial role in refining existing frameworks to better meet the needs of stakeholders. Proposals for policy refinement offer valuable insights into potential adjustments that can optimize its impact and implementation. Participant 1 explained,

"Ahh hindi siya masyadong effective kasi halimbawa para sa akin, kahit ano nlang ang maibigay ko para lang unsay ma fit sa iyahang needs, dili gyud siya effective kay dili man ko SPED teacher." (P1, IDI 3)

"It's not very effective because no matter what I provide, it doesn't really fit their needs since I'm not a SPED teacher." (P1, IDI 3)

Participant 4 further explained,

"I believe the initial phase of implementing the Masara Child Find Policy was effective. Although we lacked ample knowledge about the policy, tagging learners with learning gaps resulted in additional funds for purchasing materials for students with special needs." (P4, IDI 4)

"The initial phase of implementing the Masara Child Find Policy was effective, resulting in additional funds for purchasing learning materials for students with special needs." (P4, IDI 4)

In addition, participant 5 supported by saying,

"For me ma'am, the dissemination process and the proper assessment of identification of those students who will be tagged in the LIS po." (P5, IDI 5)

"In my opinion, the dissemination process and proper assessment are crucial for identifying students to be tagged in the LIS." (P5, IDI 5)

Theme 2 is supported by the findings of Köse and Güner-Yildiz (2021), who found that special education, as a vital aspect of education, must emphasize individualized approaches and specialized teaching methods to meet diverse needs. This findings is supported by the Theory of Multiple Intelligences of Gardner (1983) which emphasized that special education allows educators to tailor instruction to meet the specific needs of each learner, thereby enhancing engagement, motivation, and academic achievement. By embracing individualized approaches and specialized teaching methods grounded in this theory, educators can create inclusive learning environments where all students have the opportunity to succeed.

Influence Approach to Implement and Adhere to the Masara Child Find Policy

Implementing and adhering to the Masara Child Find Policy requires a proactive and systematic approach from educational stakeholders. This entails establishing clear guidelines for the identification, assessment, and support of students with learning needs. Participant 4 said,

"Child Find Policy is a good initiative of the Department of Education since it help those students with special learning needs. I also became more courageous in finding and tagging those specific students to contribute an impact to the lives of those students." (P4, IDI 4)

"The Child Find Policy by the Department of Education helps students with special needs. It has reshaped my approach to identifying and supporting students, aiming to make a positive impact on their lives." (P4, IDI 4)

Participant 5 further explained,

"My approach to implementing and adhering to the Masara Child Find Policy in a classroom would involve leveraging data analytics to identify students who may require additional support." (P5, IDI 5)

"In my classroom, I approach the implementation and adherence to the Masara Child Find Policy by utilizing data analytics to identify students needing extra support." (P5, IDI 5)

Furthermore, participant 1 added,

"Since I am not equipped to handle such cases, I don't think, I don't think that I'm effective enough." (P1, IDI 1)

"Because I lack the necessary skills to address these cases, I don't believe I am sufficiently effective." (P1, IDI 1)

Recognizing Personal Limitations and Seeking Improvement

In education, acknowledging personal limitations while striving for improvement is pivotal for effective teaching. Recognizing areas of weakness allows educators to seek growth opportunities and refine their skills. Participant 3 shared,

"Dili ko hawd, but I find ways para mas effective yung pagtuturo ko." (P3, IDI 3).

"I'm not skilled, but I find ways to make my teaching more effective." (P3, IDI 3).

Participant 1 added,

"Since I am not equipped to handle such cases, I don't think, I don't think that I'm effective enough." (P1, IDI 1).

"Since I am not equipped to handle such cases, I don't think I am effective enough." (P1, IDI 1).

Participant 5 further explained,

"My approach to implementing and adhering to the Masara Child Find Policy in a classroom would involve leveraging data analytics to identify students who may require additional support, maintaining open communication with parents and guardians." (P5, IDI 5).

"My approach to implementing and adhering to the Masara Child Find Policy in a classroom would involve leveraging data analytics to identify students who may require additional support, maintaining open communication with parents and guardians." (P5, IDI 5).

Emphasizing the Importance of Establishing Relationships

Establishing meaningful relationships is important in any educational setting as it fosters trust, understanding, and collaboration among students, teachers, and parents. Participant 3 explained,

"Dili ko hawd, but I find ways para mas effective yung pagtuturo ko." (P3, IDI 3).

"I'm not sure, but I find ways to make my teaching more effective." (P3, IDI 3).

Participant 2 further explained,

"Firstly, they should have a deep understanding of the policy and importance in protecting children from abuse. Second, teachers should establish positive relationship with students and parents, and these can contribute to creating a supporting environment." (P2, IDI 2)

"Firstly, they should have a deep understanding of the policy and its importance in protecting children from abuse. Second, teachers should establish positive relationships with students and parents, as these can contribute to creating a supportive environment." (P2, IDI 2)

Participant 5 also shared,

"My recommendation for the implementation of the Masara Child Find Policy will be the school must hire a SPED teachers for those learners with learning disabilities, and also they must request a doctor tapos it needs a budget from MOOE." (P5, IDI 5)

"My recommendation for the implementation of the Masara Child Find Policy is that the school must hire SPED teachers for learners with learning disabilities, and they must also request assistance from a doctor, which requires a budget from the MOOE." (P5, IDI 5)

Advocating for Comprehensive Approaches and Collaborative Efforts

In advocating for comprehensive approaches and collaborative efforts in education, it is essential to recognize the multifaceted nature of supporting learners with diverse needs. Participant 5 shared,

"My recommendation for the implementation of the Masara Child Find Policy will be the school must hire a SPED teachers for those learners with learning disabilities, and also they must request a doctor tapos it needs a budget from MOOE." (P5, IDI 5)

"My recommendation for implementing the Masara Child Find Policy is for the school to hire SPED teachers for learners with disabilities, and also to request assistance from a doctor, which requires budget allocation from MOOE." (P5, IDI 5)

Participant 4 further explained,

"It will became a spring-board to other schools, teachers, and policy makers who will do the same initiative." (P4, IDI 4)

"It will serve as a model for other schools, teachers, and policymakers who may undertake similar initiatives. (P4, IDI 4)

In the same vien, participant 1 also explained,

"First we need to conduct action research or study, then conduct information and dessimination drive to the stakeholders." (P1, IDI 1)

"First, we need to conduct action research or a study, then proceed with information dissemination to stakeholders." (P1, IDI 1)

Theme 3 of Objective 3 highlights the role of special education teachers in providing educational interventions for students with various learning needs, including speech disorders, cognitive deficiencies, and behavioral problems (Lawrence (2021). This concept finds additional support in the Social Learning Theory, which emphasizes the integration of observational learning, imitation, and modeling in the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and behaviors. By incorporating opportunities for students to observe, imitate, and model desired behaviors, teachers can create supportive settings that facilitate the achievement of students with diverse learning needs (Bandura, 1979).

Conclusion

Teachers' perception on including mainstream-tagged learners within the Masara Child Find Policy Framework finds inclusive education as a cornerstone for promoting equity, access, and support within the educational system. The themes and subthemes identified reflect a deep commitment among educators to create learning environments that accommodate the diverse needs of all students, regardless of background or ability. The first theme underscores the importance of promoting equity and access to education through inclusive policies and practices. Moreover, the second theme highlights the challenges faced in navigating inclusive education, including managing classroom interactions, addressing behavioral issues, and meeting parental expectations. The third theme emphasizes the role of policy implementation in supporting inclusive education.

Subsequently, teacher's strategies being employed to implement the Masara Child Find Policy can be categorized into three main themes: Firstly, teachers focus on identifying students who require additional support by employing methods such as assessment, observation, and collaboration with parents. Secondly, educators ensure adherence to the procedures outlined in the Masara Child Find Policy by following DepEd guidelines and utilizing standardized tools for systematic identification and support of students in need. Thirdly, teachers prioritize support for learners with learning disabilities by addressing individualized needs, enhancing their own preparedness through training, and facilitating resource allocation.

Furthermore, the insights gleaned from teachers' perspectives on the implementation of the Masara Child Find Policy underscore the critical need for adequate training, policy understanding, and resource allocation to effectively support learners with disabilities. Participants emphasized the importance of equipping teachers with specialized skills through training programs, particularly in the realm of special education, to better address the diverse needs of students. Additionally, there was a consensus on the significance of policy understanding, suggesting that educators require comprehensive knowledge of the policy's objectives and guidelines to facilitate its implementation. Moreover, suggestions for policy enhancement, such as conducting seminars and improving dissemination processes, were proposed to optimize the policy's effectiveness.

In conclusion, the findings from teachers' perceptions on including mainstream-tagged learners within the Masara Child Find Policy framework highlight the pivotal role of inclusive education in promoting equity, access, and support within the educational system. These insights underscore a deep commitment among educators to create inclusive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of all students. Continuous efforts are needed to provide adequate training, enhance policy understanding, and allocate resources effectively to fully support learners with disabilities and promote inclusive education practices.

Based on the comprehensive insights gathered from teachers' perceptions on inclusive education and the implementation of the Masara Child Find Policy, educational stakeholders may consider implementing the following recommendation:

Schools may consider implementing regular and comprehensive training programs for teachers, particularly focusing on special education strategies and techniques. This would enhance educators' ability to effectively support learners with diverse needs and

navigate inclusive classroom environments more confidently.

Education authorities may facilitate ongoing professional development opportunities specifically tailored to deepen teachers' understanding of inclusive policies such as the Masara Child Find Policy. Workshops, seminars, and online courses can help educators stay updated on policy revisions, best practices, and innovative approaches in inclusive education.

Collaborative efforts between schools, parents, and community stakeholders may be strengthened to ensure a holistic support system for learners with disabilities. This collaboration may involve regular communication channels, parent education workshops, and community engagement initiatives aimed at fostering a supportive environment for inclusive education.

Educational institutions may allocate sufficient resources, including funding and personnel, to support the effective implementation of inclusive policies like the Masara Child Find Policy. This may involve investing in specialized teaching materials, assistive technologies, and hiring additional staff, such as special education teachers, to cater to the diverse needs of learners.

Continuous evaluation and monitoring mechanisms may be established to assess the effectiveness and impact of inclusive education policies at the school and district levels. This may involve collecting feedback from teachers, students, parents, and other stakeholders to identify areas for improvement and inform future policy enhancements.

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